

Stability of As_2S_3 and Sb_2S_3 sols in the light of Wiersema's Method

K. L. Daluja and S. N. Srivastava

Stability of As_2S_3 and Sb_2S_3 sols has been determined quantitatively using Wiersema's method of calculation of zeta potentials. Charge density and free energy have also been evaluated by the same method. Finally the two sets of data obtained by Wiersema's method and the conventional method have been compared.

The derivation and the successive improvements of the relation between the electrophoretic mobility and the ζ -potential made by Pickard¹ contains a few additional features but so far the model and the basic equations are concerned these are similar to those of Overbeek² and Booth³. Expression due to Pickard for the electrophoretic velocity is linear in the ζ -potential. Since the relaxation force is essentially a non-linear effect, this implies that the relaxation effect is neglected. A recent treatment of the electrophoresis of a spherical particle is by Wiersema, Loeb and Overbeek⁴ (1966). The main limitation of the equations of Overbeek (loc. cit.) and Booth (loc. cit.) was that the expressions were only valid for $\zeta = 25$ mV. But the numerical solution of the problem which gives mobility as a complete power series in zeta-potential is due to Wiersema and is valid for $\zeta > 25$ mV.

Since all the stability values of the present systems depend upon the value of ζ -potentials (taken equal to ψ_s -potential it was thought worthwhile to interpret the present results in the light of the above work and compare thereby whether these two approaches have any marked difference in the values. Mention may also be made about the work of Shaw and Ottewill⁵ who studied the relaxation effect in electrophoresis of disperse system according to Wiersema method. Ottewill⁶ also reported the work of Wiersema^{7,8} for relaxation effect in electrophoresis.

Following the method of Wiersema^{4,7,8} we have calculated the zeta potentials, charge density and free energy of As_2S_3 and Sb_2S_3 sols. The two sets of data using Wiersema's method and the conventional method have been compared. The results are presented in the following Tables 1 and 2.

1. W. P. Pickard, *Proc. Roy. Soc. Lond.*, 1950, **A203**, 514; *Kolloid-Z.*, 1961 (2) **179**, 117.
2. J. Th. G. Overbeek, *Thesis Utrecht*, 1941; *Kolloid Beih.*, 1943, **54**, 257; "Advances in Colloid Science", 1950, **3**, 97.
3. F. Booth, *Nature*, 1948, **161**, 83.
4. P. H. Wiersema, A. L. Loeb and J. Th. G. Overbeek, *J. Colloid and Interface Sci.*, 1966, **22**, 78.
5. J. N. Shaw and R. H. Ottewill, *Nature*, 1965, **208**, 681.
6. D. A. Haydon and R. H. Ottewill, *Nature* (Informal Discussion of the Faraday Soc., report), 1965, **205**, 348.
7. Wiersema, Ph.D. Thesis, Utrecht., 1964, 18.
8. A. L. Loeb, J. Th. G. Overbeek and P. H. Wiersema, "The electrical double layer around a spherical colloid particle" M.I.T. Cambridge, Massachusetts, 1961, **22**, 39.

TABLE 1

Concentration of flocculating agent moles/litre $\times 10^2$	Mobility (μ /sec) (V/cm)	(Cz) [†] moles [‡] litre [‡]	l_0	$\sigma(r)$ esu/cm ² $\times 10^{-4}$	F	ϕ erg/cm ²
As ₂ S ₃ sol with NaCl at 26°						
4.00	-4.28	0.2002	24.2	4.995	26.2	7.83
4.50	-4.20	0.2124	10.8	4.025	18.8	5.97
5.00	-4.10	0.2238	8.4	3.295	13.3	4.44
5.33	-3.98	0.2311	7.0	2.835	10.8	3.73
5.66	-3.80	0.2381	5.8	2.420	8.2	2.92
5.80	-3.72	0.2410	5.3	2.240	7.5	2.70
6.00	-3.60	0.2452	5.0	2.150	6.6	2.42
Sb ₂ S ₃ sol with NaCl at 30°						
1.33	-4.66	0.1171	13.3	2.715	25.5	4.52
2.00	-4.43	0.1428	8.7	2.166	14.0	3.03
2.66	-4.15	0.1643	7.0	2.010	10.05	5.51
3.33	-4.06	0.1837	6.5	2.085	9.02	2.51
3.66	-4.91	0.1924	5.6	1.880	7.50	2.19
4.40	-3.64	0.2107	4.7	1.730	7.00	2.11
4.60	-3.80	0.2010	5.0	1.755	6.40	2.04
As ₂ S ₃ sol with DPyCl at 35°						
0.001	-5.90	0.01166	25.6	5.11	51.0	0.940
0.005	-5.26	0.01326	23.0	5.30	42.5	0.966
0.006	-5.23	0.01364	20.4	4.84	35.5	0.745
0.007	-4.62	0.01400	17.2	4.18	26.3	0.565
0.008	-3.86	0.01435	13.7	3.41	17.5	0.386
0.009	-3.49	0.01470	12.7	3.25	15.5	0.350

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The values of charge densities and free energies per surface area of these two sols in the presence of 1 : 1 electrolyte and a detergent DPyCl (dodecyl pyridinium chloride) have been presented in Table 1. A perusal of this table shows that charge density gradually decreases with increasing concentration of the electrolyte with both the sols. Similar is the case with detergent with respect to arsenic trisulphide sol. However, the only difference among these two is that the decrease in charge density is more pronounced in the case of detergent and the range is also lower than with electrolyte. Another point which is evident from the table is that the charge density increases considerably after the reversal of charge.

TABLE 2

Comparison of zeta potential calculated by two different methods

Conc. of flocculating agent $\times 10^2$	q_0	Mobility $(\mu/\text{sec})/(\text{V}/\text{cm})$	from Wiersema's method			Zeta potential mV
			E'	y_0	Zeta potential mV	
As_2S_3 sol with NaCl at 26°						
2.00	2.10	-4.60	3.38	—	—	-112.0
3.33	2.71	-4.43	3.26	—	—	-106.0
4.00	2.97	-4.28	3.145	5.10	-131.0	-98.4
4.50	3.23	-4.23	3.08	4.50	-116.0	-94.5
5.00	3.32	-4.10	3.01	3.95	-102.0	-91.5
5.33	3.43	-3.98	2.92	3.61	-92.3	-87.4
5.66	3.49	-3.80	2.79	3.24	-83.0	-81.3
5.80	3.56	-3.72	2.73	3.12	-97.5	-87.3
6.00	3.65	-3.60	2.64	2.93	-75.0	-75.4
Sb_2S_3 sol with NaCl at 30°						
1.33	1.70	-4.66	3.19	5.85	-126.0	-103.0
2.00	2.07	-4.43	3.03	3.95	-103.0	-96.0
2.66	2.38	-4.15	2.84	3.50	-91.4	-88.2
3.33	2.66	-4.06	2.78	3.33	-87.0	-84.6
3.66	2.78	-3.91	2.66	3.08	-80.4	-80.0
4.00	2.91	-3.80	2.60	3.95	-77.0	-77.0
4.40	3.05	-3.64	2.43	2.80	-73.1	-74.0
As_2S_3 sol with DPyCl at 35°						
0.001	0.209	-5.90	3.68	4.15	-110.0	-107.0
0.005	0.2295	-5.36	3.34	3.52	-104.0	-96.1
0.006	0.234	-5.23	3.26	3.57	-95.0	-89.6
0.007	0.239	-4.62	2.88	3.09	-82.0	-79.4
0.008	0.243	-3.86	2.41	2.56	-68.0	-67.4
0.009	0.249	-3.49	2.18	2.41	-54.0	-53.6

As for the free energy per unit surface area in both the cases, similar trends as with charge density have been observed. The increases in the free energy after the charge reversal is also noticed. From the above findings it seems that the increase in the charge density and free energy in both the cases after the reversal of charge may be due to the adsorption of cation while in the case of decrease with electrolyte it may be due to the neutralisation of charge. But in the case of detergent the decrease may be due to partial adsorption and thereby partial neutralisation of the charge.

The values of zeta potential calculated by the new method are reported in Table 2 where the values obtained by Overbeek's formula are also reported for comparison. The

difference between the values of zeta potential calculated by Overbeek and Wiersema methods is very small in the region of $Ka = 0.3$. However, the difference increases at higher value of Ka (≈ 3.0). It is quite clear that in the region of $Ka = 3$, probably of maximum correction region, the values calculated from the Overbeek equation are approximately 10% underestimated.

Energy V , as a function of H is calculated for $\zeta = 102$ mV ($\zeta = 91.5$ mV according to Overbeek equation) at the concentration of sodium chloride = 50 mM for arsenic trisulphide sol. Curves of V as a function of H are plotted for $\zeta = 102$ mV (from Wiersema's method) and $\zeta = 91.5$ mV (from Overbeek equation) in figure 1. The value of V_m increases from 6.5 kT to 18.1 kT by calculating zeta potential from Wiersema's work instead of Overbeek's equation. Similarly $\log V$ increases from 1.85 to 7.04.

Fig. 1. As_2S_3 sol with 50 mM NaCl 1. $\zeta = 102$ mV
(V as a function of H) 2. $\zeta = 91.5$ mV

Finally, the difference in the value of A is obtained by the method employed previously⁹. The values of $\log W$ for $\zeta = 102$ mV calculated for the different values of A and a curve is constructed between them in Fig. 2. From this curve the value of A corresponding to experimental $\log W$ (calculated from turbidity measurements) is then read off. Similar

Fig. 2. $\log W$ as a function of Hamaker constant, A (the dotted lines indicate the values of A corresponding to W calculated turbidimetrically).

curve for $\zeta = 91.5$ mV also depicted in the same figure. The value obtained for A is 2.26×10^{-12} ergs for $\zeta = 102$ mV, while for $\zeta = 91.5$ mV it is 1.26×10^{-12} ergs. However, there is not much difference between the two values of A . Energy V , as a function of H is also calculated for $\zeta = 87$ mV ($\zeta = 84.6$ mV from Overbeek equation) for Sb_2S_3 sol with 33.3 mM NaCl. Curves between V and H are constructed for $\zeta = 87$ mV (from Wiersema method) and 84.6 mV (for Overbeek equation) and are given in Fig. 3. Here V_m increases from 1.98 kT to 2.8 kT when zeta potential is calculated from Wiersema method instead of Overbeek formula. Values of $\log W$ consequently also increases from 0.126 to 0.490. To calculate the values of A for Sb_2S_3 sol curves are plotted between $\log W$ (for $\zeta = 87$ mV and also for $\zeta = 84.6$ mV) and various values of A (Fig. 4) from these curves the values of A corresponding to experimental value of $\log W$ are then read off. $A = 1.16 \times 10^{-12}$ ergs

Fig. 3. Sb_2S_3 sol with 33.3 mM NaCl
 1. $\zeta = 87$ mV
 2. $\zeta = 84.6$ mV
 V as a function of H .

Fig. 4. Sb_2S_3 sol with 33.3 mM NaCl. $\log W$ as a function of Hamaker constant A .

is obtained corresponding to 87 mV zeta potential while 1.07×10^{-12} ergs is obtained for zeta potential $\zeta = 84.7$ mV. It is quite clear that the values of A evaluated against two different values of zeta potential calculated by two different methods for the same mobility value are almost the same.

However, the Wiersema method has its own limitations. Computation data for 1 : 1 electrolyte are reported only upto $y_0 = 6$. In case of detergents some times values go upto 6 and even more, so it is not possible to calculate zeta potential at these higher values. Also the calculation of zeta potential could not be attempted for 2 : 1 and 3 : 1 electrolytes because the tabulated data of y_0 for unsymmetrical electrolytes are not upto 6 as required for the present work.

Department of Chemistry,
Agra College,
Agra.

Received August 17, 1968
Revised MSS received July 9, 1970.